

hectares in India. The productivity of the crop is often challenged by water stress, drought, biotic stresses like pests and diseases and constraints related with nutrient management. In recent years, leaf web worm, *Acria* sp. is inflicting severe damage to oil palm leaves apart from bag worms. Although it was initially observed on oil palm, that too in some areas, now it is damaging even coconut. The population is slowly spreading and it was observed to cause damage in many oil palm gardens in West Godavari and Krishna districts of Andhra Pradesh. A yield loss of up to 34.0 per cent was reported for leaf web worm, *Acria* sp. in oil palm. The information regarding its life history, damage, leaf eating potential, natural enemies association and seasonal activity are not available sufficiently in the known literature. Hence, a systematic study was carried out on the above aspects for using them in formulating the integrated pest management strategies in oil palm. The incubation period was ranging from 4-6 days with an average period of 4.7 days. The percentage of egg hatchability was 95.6 with ranging from 92.8-100 per cent. The larvae was greenish in colour with whitish dorsal line in the middle of the body. The larval stage passed through 7 instars in a period of about 20.7 days. After the larva was full grown, it stopped feeding and reduced in size and entered to pre-pupal stage, which lasted for 1 day. The pupal stage lasted for about 5.8 days. Adult lived for about 5.4 days on an average. The total life period from egg to adult stage was ranging from 30-44 days. Each female laid about 62.5 eggs which ranged from 25-103 eggs in groups (in confined condition). However under field condition the eggs were laid singly. The male and female sex ratio was 48: 52 (Male: Female). It was found that individual larvae of leaf web worm consumed about 655.6 mm² of leaf area to complete its stage. During the investigation, it was observed that the larvae of leaf web worm were found parasitized by two biocontrol agents, namely *Apanteles hyposidrae* (Braconidae; Hymenoptera) and *Elasmus brevicornis* (Elasmidae; Hymenoptera) causing 87.5 to 100.0 and 3.9 to 23.4 per cent parasitism respectively. Apart from these two parasitoids, a pupal parasitoid *Brachymeria* sp. was also observed and found to cause around 80.0 per cent parasitism.

TS8: P1

Influence of abiotic factors on insect-pests of ber (*Ziziphus mauritiana* Lam.) in arid region of Rajasthan

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Indian jujube known as ber (*Ziziphus mauritiana* Lam.) is an extremely drought resistant native fruit of India. It is a dominant component of the natural vegetation in the Indian "Thar desert". However, the quality and productivity of fruits is adversely affected by insect pests, which ultimately lead to significant yield loss and deterioration in market value. Though as many as 130 species of insect pests have been recorded in India, a total of 10 insect-pests feeding on ber were recorded from hot arid region of Rajasthan. Out of these, two insects viz., ber fruit fly (*Carpomyia vesuviana* Costa) and stone weevil (*Aubeus himalayanus* Voss) were recorded as major pests with infestation varying from high to very high degree and two insects (Ber butter fly, *Tarucus theophrastus* (Fabricius) and thrips, *Scirtothrips dorsalis* (Hood)) were recorded as moderate pests. Rest six insects viz., grey weevil, *Myllocerus dentifer* (Fabricius), *M. blandus* Faust, *Amblyrrhinus poricollis* Schoenherr; leaf webber, *Synclera univocolis*; bark eating caterpillars, *Indarbela* sp and termite, *Odontotermes* sp were recorded as minor pests. The incidence of fruit fly (*C. vesuviana*) and stone weevil (*A. himalayanus*) were recorded on ber

from October to February. The damage of leaf feeder's viz., ber butterfly, leaf webber, thrips and grey weevils damage was more during June to September. The high mean percent incidence of fruit fly was recorded on gola (16.77%) than seb (10.36%) but stone weevil incidence was found reverse to fruit fly (more in seb, 15.43 % than gola, 9.62 %). Correlation of fruit fly and stone weevil with maximum and minimum temperatures was found negative, which indicated that decrease in temperatures increased the population of the pest. Correlation between the pest (fruit fly & stone weevil) population and maximum and minimum R.H. was found positive.

TS8: P2

Standardization of fumigation technique for Protected carnation cultivation

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Carnation is one of the most important cut flower which is grown under protected environment. Soil sterilization is done for controlling the harmful soil borne pathogens inside the protected structures. Carnation being a semi perennial cut flower crop, and the total duration of the crop is 24 months, fumigation needs to be done for effective check on the soil borne pathogens especially fusarium wilt. Dazomet (tetrahydro -3,5- dimethyl-2H-1,3,5 thiodiazine-2-thione), a halogen free microgranular, cost effective soil fumigant is used for disinfecting the soil borne fungi, bacteria, nematodes, soil insects and weed seeds. It is applied @ 30 g per square metre, at a depth of 15 cm in the soil. Dazomet upon mixing with soil oxygen and water releases, Methyl Iso Thio Cyanate and it further breaks down to carbon disulphide, formaldehyde, hydrogen sulphide and ammonia. The breakdown of the chemical is very rapid on moist aerobic soil. Due course of time, Dazomet upon degradation mineralizes into plant nutrients as ammonium, nitrate, sulphate and carbonate ions which helps the seedlings to grow healthy and vigorously. Immediately after application, soil has to be completely covered with LDPE sheets and allow it to react for 7-9 days. Fumigation creates the space for beneficial organisms to populate the area and also control the target crop pests and diseases. Hence, the normal natural balance and the resulting environmental benefits are restored in favour of the crop.

TS8: P3

Standardization of eco-friendly methods to manage mites (*Tetranychus urticae*) infesting carnation (*Dianthus caryophyllus* Linn.)

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Carnation (*Dianthus caryophyllus* L.) is one among the most popular commercial cut flowers of the world, ranking second in commercial importance next to rose. There are a number of

